

Reactions of Tungsten (VI) Oxytetrachloride with Phenols and Nitrophenols

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The interaction of tungsten (VI) oxytetrachloride with some mono-, di-, and trihydroxyphenols and mono- and dinitrophenols has been studied; the properties of the phenoxides formed have been studied and their constitutions discussed.

No work appears to have been done on the action of tungsten (VI) oxytetrachloride on phenols and nitrophenols. Funk and Baumann (*Z. anorg. allgem., Chem.*, 1937, 231, 264) studied the action of WCl_6 on phenol and β -naphthol. The present authors studied the interaction of WCl_6 with phenols and nitrophenols (this *Journal*, 1960, 27, 681). The work has now been extended to study the action of some mono-, di-, and trihydroxyphenols, and mono- and dinitrophenols on tungsten (VI) oxytetrachloride.

EXPERIMENTAL

Tungsten (VI) oxytetrachloride was prepared by the method described earlier (this *Journal* 38, 352). The organic solvents were dried and distilled. The phenols and nitrophenols used were of B. D. H. or Merck's 'extra pure' quality.

General Method of Preparation—To liquid or low melting phenols or nitrophenols, dissolved in benzene, $WOCl_4$ in CS_2 was added. The mixture was then heated on a water bath till evolution of HCl ceased.

Other phenols and nitrophenols were similarly dissolved in benzene and $WOCl_4$ in CS_2 was added to them; but in these cases the mixture was gently warmed on an oil bath till the solvents evaporated off. The temperature of the bath was then raised 10-15° higher than the m.p. of the respective phenol or nitrophenol, and heating continued till HCl ceased to evolve.

The products obtained in both the cases were washed with benzene till free of phenols or nitrophenols and dried in a vacuum desiccator. Tungsten was estimated as WO_3 and the percentages of tungsten and the empirical formulas of the compounds were calculated from the weights of WO_3 obtained. Carbon and hydrogen were estimated by combustion method in four of the compounds and nitrogen by Duma's method in two.

DISCUSSION

All the compounds are coloured, insoluble in common organic solvents except ethanol and acetone in which they are sparingly soluble. They are very stable in dry atmosphere but hydrolyse slowly on boiling with water or with dilute alkali solutions. These do not give sharp m.p. but decompose when heated.

On analysis it is found that one molecule of tungsten (VI) oxytetrachloride reacts with four molecules of a monohydroxy and two molecules of a dihydroxy or trihydroxy

TABLE I

Phenols.	Compound formed.	Colour.	% Tungsten.		% Carbon.		% Hydrogen.	
			Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
A. Tungsten(VI) oxytetrachloride with monohydroxyphenol. $WOCl_4$; phenol=1:1.								
1. Phenol	$WO(C_6H_5O)_4$	Dirty green	32.40	32.17	..	..	..	..
2. α -Naphthol	$WO(C_{10}H_7O)_4$	black	23.82	23.83	61.53	62.18	3.58	3.63
3. β -Naphthol	-Do-	Pale yellow	23.74	23.83	..	..	..	..
4. <i>o</i> -Cresol	$WO(CH_3-C_6H_4O)_4$	Grey	20.70	20.20	..	..	..	..
5. <i>m</i> -Cresol	-Do-	Yellowish green	20.48	20.20	..	..	..	..
6. <i>p</i> -Cresol	-Do-	Yellowish brown	20.19	20.20	..	..	..	..
B. Tungsten (VI) oxytetrachloride with dihydroxyphenol. $WOCl_4$; phenol=1:2.								
7. Resorcinol	$WO(C_6H_4O_2)_4$	Brown	44.14	44.23	34.23	34.62	1.91	1.92
8. Catechol	$WO(C_6H_4O_2)_2$	Black	44.62	44.23	..	..	..	..
9. Hydroquinone	$WO(C_6H_4O_2)_2$	-Do-	44.53	44.23	..	..	..	..
10. Orcinol	$WO(CH_3-C_6H_3O_2)_2$	-Do-	40.88	41.44	..	..	..	..
C. Tungsten (IV) oxytetrachloride with trihydroxyphenol. $WOCl_4$; phenol=1:2.								
11. Pyrogallol	$WO(C_6H_3O_3.OH)_2$	-Do-	40.61	41.07	32.37	32.15	1.74	1.79
12. Phloroglucinol	$WO(C_6H_3O_3.OH)_2$	Brown	40.79	41.07	..	..	..	..

TABLE II

Nitrophenol.	Compound formed.	Colour.	% Tungsten.		% Carbon.		% Hydrogen.		% Nitrogen.	
			Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.
1. <i>o</i> -Nitrophenol	$WO(NO_2.C_6H_4O)_4$	Brown	24.60	24.46	36.09	36.31	2.07	2.13	7.33	7.45
2. <i>m</i> -Nitrophenol	-Do-	Deep brown	24.78	24.46	..	..	..	..	..	..
3. <i>p</i> -Nitrophenol	-Do-	Brownish black	24.22	24.46	..	..	..	..	..	..
4. 1-Nitroso 2-naphthol	$WO(NO.C_{10}H_6O)_4$	Shining black	21.04	20.72	..	..	..	..	..	..
5. 2,4-Dinitrophenol	$WO[(NO_2)_2.C_6H_3O]_4$	Brownish black	19.62	19.74	..	..	..	..	11.66	12.01
6. 2,4-Dinitro α -naphthol	$WO[(NO_2)_2.C_{10}H_5O]_4$	Pitch black	18.06	18.25	..	..	..	..	..	..

phenols, and the corresponding phenoxides are formed. The compounds formed may be represented as :

in the case of mono- and dihydroxy phenols respectively. Nitro and dinitrophenols give similar compounds, only the hydroxy group being affected.

In the case of pyrogallol and phloroglucinol, only two hydrogen atoms are displaced from the three hydroxyl groups present in them. From the experiments carried out it is not possible to find the position of free OH-group, and therefore no definite structure can be assigned to these compounds formed.

The authors' sincere thanks are due to the authorities of the Banaras Hindu University for providing facilities.

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Received December 12, 1960.